

NEEDS ANALYSIS REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Needs analysis plays a crucial role upon designing and teaching any language course, it does not matter whether it is English for Specific Purposes or general English course. Thus, the importance of needs analysis has been underlined by numerous scholars and authors. According to Iwai et al. (1999), the term needs analysis generally means the activities that are involved in collecting information that will assist as fundamentals to develop a curriculum that will meet the needs of a group of students. He also mentions that formal needs analysis far new in language teaching, even though, informal needs analysis was carried out in order to identify weaknesses and strengths of students. Iwai, as well as, define the appearance new approaches, replacement of old methods and intentions to meet the needs of students. Johns (1991) states that needs analysis is the primary step to take while designing any course because it can guarantee valid and relevant activities for the subsequent course.

Key words: analysis, Online English, improvement skills. Learners' profile.

I have chosen my sister as an agent for my needs analysis report as I have been teaching her for six months. Her name is Feruza Murodova, she is 16 years old . she is making best effort as an applicant so as to be enrolled in one of the Korean institutes successfully. She has less than two years of experience in language learning. Since she noticed an innate ability and appearance of sudden interest in acquiring language she has been making valuable effort to master the language. Her aspirations from learning the language are multiple and they vary from the slightest to the biggest. In regards of huge desires she is planning to get accepted into bachelor's degree as a successful applicant and continue to do her master's degree in one of the countries of the world which suggests world-class education. When it goes about small intentions, reading original version of books and savoring real taste of movies in English. Admittedly, Feruza is so inspired and want to keep equal balance of the improvement of all skills at the same time, therefore, she typically addresses learning strategies to raise the efficiency of her learning process. Besides, upon being exposed to English books and movies she tends to develop her sociocultural competence through comparing and contrasting special features of traditions in both countries.

Procedure

To achieve a satisfactory ultimate result I applied numerous activities and type of tests:

1. Online English level test
2. Test your English /Cambridge English
3. Introvert/ Extrovert/ Ambivert test
4. Needs Analysis Questionnaire for EFL Students

Initially, in the hope of a precise insight into the level of my student I made a decision on providing two types of language proficiency level test to her that are offered by British Council and Cambridge. Having analyzed the extent to which she is proficient in language use, I aspired to clarify her personality trait. Because being certain about the type of personality will assist a teacher to apparently figure out the needs of his/her student. Thus, mentors may happen to select relevant materials to satisfactorily meet the needs of learners. Moreover, what I would prefer mentioning is that raising awareness about students' learning styles, considering their age, interests, learning atmosphere and even their background may make a significant sense while identifying learners' needs. As a matter of fact, I employed simple test to ascertain her learning style which showed that she was far efficient in learning with the help of visual aids and constant movement of her and the teacher in the classroom. Therefore, one can draw conclusion that she is predominantly visual and partially kinesthetic learner. Subsequently, I asked Feruza to complete online needs analysis questionnaire which was adopted in Tashkent, Uzbekistan to identify weaknesses and strengths of her and assess appropriately what she truly needs.

Findings

Upon conducting needs analysis I managed to notice some lacks of the learner. Although her knowledge in language has considerably increased within this short period of time, she is still continuing to make small but silly mistakes in grammar which was apparently noticeable when I analyzed her results. She can easily deal with complicated questions, however, when it comes to tiny rules she is at times failing to cope with trivial grammatical rules. In addition, since she is struggling to enhance her abilities in reading, writing, listening and speaking at once, this is hindering her improvement in all skills. Because I was apparent that all-skills –at-once method is somehow overwhelming for her. So relevant syllabus should be developed for her to provide stability and balance of acquiring all skills. It is impossible not to recognize that she has an excellent command of knowledge, yet as an upcoming teacher I would suggest her to work on communicative competence and reinforce her speaking skills in real life communications.

Suggestions

Observation of lessons at school encouraged me to provide some suggestions on the improvement of the classroom. They are followings:

- No matter how modern life we are living in primary focus of the lesson is still on grammar translation method. Instead, they had better enhance their feasible skills, communicative and sociocultural competence to be fluent user in the language;
- I would suggest getting rid of the dominance of teacher in the control of the lesson and letting students to take the lead in learning process;
- I would like to point to the topics and contents of the textbooks at school which needs an incredible improvement. To be more clear, provision a set of topics that are socially and globally important and serve to broaden the horizon of students would guarantee the efficiency of knowledge obtaining process;
- Increase in the frequency of the conducting English classes would facilitate language obtaining process;
- Since evaluation makes a huge difference the progress of students sufficient amount of work should be done to enhance assessing process.

Conclusion

To sum up, having carried out Needs Analysis I not only obtained valuable experience in the area of needs analysis, but also learned a lot about different steps to take so as to complete the process. Significantly, I came to realize the underlying reason of conducting needs analysis and its feasible benefits to the efficient classroom and for the development of relevant syllabus. Additionally, in order to accomplish the task I was exposed to several challenges that are contributory factor for my personal and professional career. Besides, I happened to address plentiful type of websites and employ relevant test for my learner through improving my IT skills. To put it simply, I was provided opportunity to obtain both theoretical and practical knowledge on Needs Analysis.

References:

1. Mehdi Haseli Songhori (2008) Introduction to Needs Analysis.
2. Richards, J. C. (2001) Curriculum Development in Language Teaching. Cambridge. CUP.
3. Michael H. Long (2005) Methodological issues in learner needs analysis.

Appendix

1. Online English level test -- <https://www.cambridgeenglish.org/test-your-english/>

2. Test your English / Cambridge English-- <https://learnenglish.britishcouncil.org/online-english-level-test>

Test your English - your results

Well done for completing the test!

Your score is 21 out of 25

[Review your answers](#)

Your score means you might be ready to prepare for **B2 First** or **C1 Advanced**.

3. Introversion/Extroversion/ Ambivert test -- <https://ideas.ted.com/quiz-are-you-an-extrovert-introvert-or-ambivert/>

5/10 • Результат 50%
Результат: You are an ambivert.

Поделиться Результатом

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Extroverts tend to be outgoing and bold. They gravitate toward roles that put them in the center of attention. **Introverts** tend to be quiet and deliberative. They prefer one-on-one meetings, working on their own, and long walks on the beach (just kidding). **Ambiverts** fall in the middle of the spectrum, and they're equally comfortable in leadership and supporting roles, and they tend to adapt to fill voids in their teams.

4. Needs Analysis Questionnaire --

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1UXD1F5hLySM4pT6Z-5SHX4uKAKZLA1qKguHH_MAvN1M/edit

Needs Analysis Questionnaire for EFL Students.

Your response has been recorded.

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